

Knowledge and Attitude of Teachers' Toward Students with Learning Disabilities in Senior Secondary Schools in Rivers State, Nigeria

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Abstract

The study investigated teachers' knowledge and attitude towards students with learning disabilities in regular secondary schools in Rivers State" Descriptive research design was used for the study. Two research questions (2) and two hypotheses (2) were formulated to guide the study. The population of the study comprised all the public secondary school teachers in Rivers State estimated at 7,179. Stratified random sampling technique was used to draw a sample size of 400 Secondary School Teachers for the Study. A self-structured questionnaire titled Teacher's Knowledge and Attitude towards Students with Special Needs Questionnaire (TKASNQ) was used to collect data for the study. TKASNQ was validated by two other experts in Special Needs Education. The reliability index of TKASNQ was established by Cronbach Alpha method and the indices were $\alpha=0.75$ for (KTASNQ), $(TKQ)\alpha=0.86$ and $(TAQ)\alpha=0.84$. The research questions were answered using mean score and standard deviation while independent t-test were used in testing the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. Findings from the study indicated that majority of the teachers showed good knowledge of students with learning disabilities in regular secondary schools in Rivers State, Consequently, the revealed shows that teachers from Pentecostal religion had a higher mean rating than their counterparts from the Orthodox religion concerning their attitude towards students with learning disabilities in secondary schools in Rivers State. There is no significant difference in the mean rating of teachers' knowledge towards students with learning disabilities in regular secondary schools in Rivers State based on gender, and there is significant difference in the mean ratings of teachers' attitude towards students with learning disabilities in secondary schools in Rivers State based on religion. Hence, the null hypothesis eleven was rejected at 0.05 level of significance. Based on the findings, conclusions were made. The following recommendations were made; Schools should implement inclusive practices to ensure that all students, including those with learning disabilities, receive appropriate support and accommodations to succeed academically, and the Rivers State government should prioritize providing continuous training and professional development opportunities for male and female teachers to enhance their knowledge and skills in supporting students with learning disabilities.

Introduction

Placing the student with learning disabilities in education set up certainly requires the collaboration of both teachers', students and others. Kapinga (2020) averred that for education approach to be successfully implemented, a number of stakeholders including teachers', must become fully involved. This is because the psychological and social disposition of the student with learning disabilities in the

classroom may be affected by the level of acceptance they receive from teachers' in the nature of interaction that exists amongst them. It is to this end that Salend (1990) pointed out that teachers' also play a large role in the success or failure of mainstreaming children with learning disabilities. If those without learning disabilities interact positively with their peers who have learning disabilities by serving as role models, peer tutors and friends then success is more likely to occur (Salend, 1990). However, Salend (1990) observed that the majority of studies indicated that the teachers' demonstrate negative attitudes toward disabled children and this can have a negative impact on the goals and school achievement, social and emotional adjustment, in-class behaviour and attitudes toward school and self of a child with a disability such as learning disabilities.

Learning disabilities (LD) are lifelong disabilities that affect a person's life and are characterized by a significant difference in a person's achievements. A student with a learning disability may show one or more of the following characteristics: Difficulty in reading, writing, written expression, spelling, mathematics calculation, or mathematics reasoning, or having memory and perception problems, speech and language disorders, and being easily distracted and difficulty while having to sit still.

Sawhney and Bansal (2014) described learning disabilities as delays, deviations and performance discrepancies in the basic academic subjects e.g arithmetic, reading, writing, and spelling as well as speech and cannot be attributed to mental retardation, sensory deficits, or emotional disturbances or learning disabilities. It is a general educational term, an umbrella label-that includes a variety of different conditions. Unfortunately, most of these children are never identified as learning disabled. Due to a lack of awareness among teachers', parents and school authorities, these children are usually labelled as slow, behind, incapable and failures.

The concept of knowledge is very crucial to the development and survival of man globally. Its scope cuts across every sphere of life and it plays a prominent role in every activity man engages himself with. Experts in science and social sciences have attempted to conceptualize knowledge in many ways. In philosophy, the branch that deals with the study of knowledge is known as epistemology while psychologists consider the concept of knowledge under the cognitive domain of learning. Although, there is so far no consensus on the definition of knowledge, scholars are in agreement that it has to do with acquiring new facts about something through the learning process. Understanding knowledge and knowing how to systematically enhance it is therefore, one of the major tasks of public health experts in their quest to ensure the adoption of recommended behaviours. This is in line with the findings of similar studies among Thai and Belgian University Students (Drongritichai, 2012; Degroote et al. 2014). This suggests that teachers' with high knowledge of basic issues about children with learning disabilities are more likely to exhibit positive attitudes towards them

Also, a study carried out in Italy using the Information-Motivation and Behavioural Skills model revealed that adherence-related information which is targeted at improving the level of knowledge,

has a significant relationship to adherence-related behavioural skills, while behavioural skills in turn, were also significantly associated with self-reported optimal adherence (Fisher et al. 2006).

Techear knowledge and attitude of student with learning disabilities in secondary schools in Rivers state were examined in this study.

Attitude is one of the affective areas which had been very much studied. It is not easy for scholars to have a consensus on a definition of attitudes (Krosnick et al. 2005) or when defined, it has come in myriad ways (Fabrigar, 2005). Concerning the aim of the current study, a kind of positive- or -negative - evaluation-based definition seemed applicable. One of those is the definition advanced by Eagly and Chaiken:

“Attitude is a psychological tendency that is expressed by evaluating a particular entity with some degree of favour or disfavour” (2016, p1).

Alharthi and Evans (2017) studied the attitudes of SETs towards teaching students with learning disabilities in regular classrooms and found that the attitudes of SETs towards inclusive education were positive and that no significant differences existed between teachers' attitudes based on their gender. On the other hand, Ogunsola (2017) argued that within the Nigerian school setting, some teachers demonstrate negative attitudes towards students with learning disabilities in their classrooms. Also, negative teachers' attitudes toward teaching students with learning disabilities in the regular classroom have been documented in the professional research literature (deBoer, Pijil & Minnaert, 2011). Such attitudes tend to compound the problems of students with learning disabilities.

Attitudes predispose individuals to actions that have some degree of consistency and can be evaluated as either negative or positive (Fishbein&Ajzen, 1975; McMillen, Seastrom, Gruber, McGrath & Cohen, 2000). A positive attitude towards all students in the regular classroom irrespective of the learning challenges of the students will contribute immensely towards the high levels of academic achievement and overall benefits of schooling obtained by the students. Positive attitudes displayed by teachers and entire school staff will encourage the attainment of inclusive and equitable quality education for all learners particularly those with learning disabilities. Vaz, Wilson, Falkmer, Sim, Scott and Cordier (2015) examined primary school teachers' attitudes towards inclusion of students with all disabilities in regular schools in Western Australia and the factors associated with teachers' attitudes towards inclusion. The findings showed that four teacher attributes (age, gender, teaching self-efficacy and training) collectively explained 42 per cent of the variability in teachers' attitude toward including students with disabilities.

Kelechi (2019) findings, revealed that there was no significant gender difference in the knowledge of the roles of regular and special education teachers in the education of students with learning disabilities. However, a significant gender difference in the attitude of teachers towards their roles in the education of students with learning disabilities. The result further showed that female regular and

special education teachers obtained a more positive attitude towards their roles than male regular and special education teachers in the education of students with learning disabilities.

Thronsdén and Turmo (2012) conducted a study on differences in male and female teachers' beliefs about mathematics instruction and reported that teachers had good mastery of their subject and instructional approaches. However, female teachers had somewhat higher levels of mastery goals for students and mastery approaches to instruction, while male teachers had a somewhat higher level of performance approaches to instruction. By inference, the teachers were knowledgeable about their roles. Also, the teachers had high personal teaching efficacy to complement their mastery goals. Furthermore, the findings of a study conducted in Tanzania by Moses, Admiraal and Berry (2016) showed that there was no significant relationship between gender and commitment of teachers to teaching. Thronsdén and Turmo (2012) evinced that female teachers appear to be more student-centred and supportive of students than male teachers. Female teachers also tend to adopt class discussion method more often than male teachers and encourage collaborative learning practices.

On the hand, The Christian teachers' community has a long history of negative attitudes towards people with disabilities. Eiesland (2009) reiterated that the church has too long provided ideological funding and charitable practices to people with disabilities which result in marginalisation. Eiesland (2009) further asserted that—Our bodies have too often been touched by hands that have forgotten our humanity and attend only to curing us...Healing has been the churchly parallel to rehabilitative medicine, in which the goal was normalisation'of the bodies of people with disabilities.

This implies that the Christian teachers' has a flawed focus on healing people with disability instead of accepting their condition. The church has to understand that people with disability are another brand of the image of God and have to be recognised in their own condition. Wolfensberger (1998) stated that people with disabilities are marginalised when society views them as an object of charity or as someone who is sick and needs to be healed. He further pointed out that the Christian teachers' devalues people with disability by viewing them as the other or alien. Reinders (2008) stated that the prevailing Roman Catholic teachers' view regards the life of a person with profound disabilities as a manifestation of natural evil.

Therefore, it is important to be able to understand the knowledge attitude of teachers' towards students with learning disabilities in senior secondary school in Rivers State. This is imperative because, despite the introduction of policies that promote inclusive education, it has not been sufficient to bring about the anticipated level of change in secondary schools. Some of the obstacles experienced by students with learning disabilities are associated with how best they can be accepted by their teachers' and interact meaningfully without fear or timidity due to stigmatization.

Statement of the Problem

One of the greatest challenges of students with learning disabilities (LDs) is the attitude of people towards their condition. There is an increasing number of students with learning disabilities in public schools, and the inclusion of students with learning disabilities in a education ought to be beneficial, not only to the students with learning disabilities but to all other students and teachers' in schools because it enhances social integration. Learning disabilities is a disorder and mental incapacitation confronting pupils and students thereby affecting their ability to assimilate, scrutinize and utilize information and learned concepts to enhance their performance (i.e. curricular and extracurricular) in the entire educational process.

However, it is unfortunate to note that the support expected from public secondary school teachers' in Rivers State towards students with learning disabilities is not visible. Thus, one of the barriers to increasing access for students with learning disabilities to mainstream schools is the negative attitudes of teachers'. This can have dramatic effects on the lives of young students with learning disabilities, resulting in difficulties in joining group activities, declining academic performance, dropping out of school and/or problem behaviour. In worst-case scenarios, rejection and bullying may lead to negative long-term outcomes, such as depression and other mental health issues. Therefore, it is important to understand the attitudes and knowledge of teachers' towards persons with learning disabilities in the schooling system. This is imperative because, despite the introduction of policies that promote inclusive education, it has not been sufficient to bring about the anticipated level of change in secondary schools. Some of the obstacles experienced by students with learning disabilities are associated with how best they can be accepted by their teachers' and interact meaningfully without fear or timidity due to stigmatization.

It is in view of the above that this study attempts to investigate the knowledge and attitude of teachers' towards students with learning disabilities in secondary schools in Rivers State.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What is the level of teachers' knowledge towards students with learning disabilities in secondary schools in Rivers State based on Gender.
2. What is the level of teachers' Attitude towards students with learning disabilities in secondary schools in Rivers State based on religion.

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were formulated to guide the study

1. There is no significant difference in the mean rating of teachers' knowledge towards students with learning disabilities in secondary schools in Rivers State based on gender.

2. There is no significant difference in the mean rating of teachers' Attitude towards students with learning disabilities in secondary schools in Rivers State based on religion

Methodology

This study made use of descriptive survey research design to investigate secondary school teachers' knowledge and attitude towards special needs students in Rivers State. The population of this study consisted of all the teachers' in senior secondary schools in the twenty-three (23) Local Government Areas of Rivers State, estimated to be seven thousand one hundred and seventy nine teachers' (7,179), (Source: Planning, Research and Statistics Department, RSSSSB, Port Harcourt, Rivers State. 2021). Sample size of 400 teachers' were selected using stratified random sampling technique through the Yaro Yemane formula. Multi-stage sampling technique was used to divide the state into three senatorial districts viz; Rivers West, River South East and River East. From each of the of the senatorial districts the researcher will select 120 teachers'. One hundred and sixty (160) teachers' were selected from River South East because it has the largest population of secondary school Students. This ensured adequate representation of the population under the study. It also ensured that all the variables of the study (gender and religion) were represented. A total of (400) teachers' were selected as samples for the study, (200 male and 200 female teachers') in Rivers State. The researcher made use of a self-constructed questionnaire titled "Teacher's Knowledge and Attitude towards students with Special Needs Questionnaire" (TKASNQ). The questionnaire was used to gather data for the study.(TKASNQ) will be responded on a four-point modified Likert scale format of Always=4, Sometimes=3, Rarely=2 and Never=1.

The "Teacher's Knowledge and Attitude towards students with Special Needs Questionnaire" (TKASNQ) reliability was determined using the Cronbach Alpha Reliability Method. The reliability indices were established as $\alpha = 0.75$ for (TKASNQ), Teachers Knowledge Questionnaire (TKG) and Teachers Attitude Questionnaire (TAG) $r = 0.84$ respectively. The data collected was analyzed using mean and standard deviation to answer the research questions while independent t-test were used to analyse the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance.

Results

Research Question One: What are the mean ratings of teachers' knowledge towards students with learning disabilities in secondary schools in Rivers State based on gender?

Table 1: Summary of Mean Ratings and Standard Deviation of Teachers' Knowledge towards Students with Learning Disabilities in Secondary Schools in Rivers State based on Gender

S/N	Items	Male (n = 200)		Female (n = 200)	
		\bar{x}	SD	\bar{x}	SD
.1	There are students with different types of learning disabilities in my school.	3.18	0.80	3.34	0.73
.2	I am very familiar with most types of learning disabilities like dyslexia dyscalculia, dysgraphia, dyspraxia, dysphasia & ADHD and how they manifest among students.	3.30	0.73	3.23	0.77
.3	I have taught students with most of the common types of learning disabilities in different classes in my years of teaching experience	3.45	0.63	3.40	0.67
.4	There are students in my class who read slowly and painfully	3.17	0.76	3.09	0.81
.5	I have taught students who have trouble with spelling	3.14	0.80	3.10	0.81
.6	I have taught students who cannot easily recall words	3.23	0.77	3.29	0.74
.7	There are students who cannot decode errors especially with the order of letters in my classes	3.45	0.64	3.34	0.70
.8	I have taught students who have difficulty with written language	3.19	0.76	3.12	0.79
.9	There are students who have writing problems in my classes	3.12	0.78	3.13	0.78
.10	Students with written language and reading problems manifest attributes of dyslexia	3.16	0.76	3.14	0.79
.11	There are students with difficulties in simple arithmetic in my class	3.21	0.75	3.07	0.82
.12	There are students in my class who have difficulties in calculating figures in terms of addition, subtraction, division or multiplication	3.28	0.71	3.16	0.83
.13	There are students who are always falling sick on the days of the week that the subject mathematics is to be taught in my class	3.16	0.76	3.11	0.85
.14	There are students who always avoid activities that involve mathematics in my class	3.21	0.78	3.11	0.86
.15	There are students in my class who have difficulty in understanding mathematical symbols such as plus (+) and minus (-) signs	3.12	0.81	2.97	0.85
.16	There students who are always afraid whenever mathematical formula is written on the board due to	3.05	1.03	3.03	0.97

	difficulty in understanding formulae				
.17	Students with arithmetic and mathematical problems manifest attributes of a form of learning disability called dyscalculia	3.41	0.68	3.54	0.62
.18	I have taught students with illegible printing and cursive writing	3.05	0.86	3.07	0.80
.19	I have taught students who have difficulties with the use of upper cases	3.22	0.81	3.22	0.70
.20	I have taught students who have difficulties with the use of lower cases	3.53	0.67	3.43	0.54
.21	There are students with inconsistency in spacing words and letters	3.20	0.78	3.19	0.66
.22	I have taught students who always have unfinished or omitted words	3.27	0.78	3.30	0.74
.23	There are students in my class with cramped or unusual grip of pen	3.08	0.93	3.04	0.84
.24	Students with deficits in motor skills show attributes of dysgraphia	3.21	0.77	3.35	0.56
.25	Students with difficulties in motor coordination manifest attributes of dyspraxia	3.27	0.79	3.32	0.64
	Grand Mean	3.23		3.20	

Criterion Mean = 2.5, Mean: 1.0-2.49 = Disagreed, 2.5-4.00= Agreed

Table1: reveals the mean ratings of teachers' knowledge towards students with learning disabilities in secondary schools in Rivers State based on gender. The result from the male teachers revealed that majority agreed to items 1-25 with mean scores greater than or equal to the criterion mean of 2.5. Also, the result from the female teachers revealed that majority agreed to items 1-25 with mean scores greater than or equal to the criterion mean of 2.5. However, the grand mean of 3.23 for male teachers and 3.20revealed that majority of the male and female teachers showed good knowledge of students with learning disabilities in secondary schools in Rivers State, with no substantial mean difference.

Research Question Two: What are the mean ratings of teachers' attitude towards students with learning disabilities in secondary schools in Rivers State based on religion?

Table 4.13: Summary of Mean Ratings and Standard Deviation of Teachers' Attitude towards Students with Learning Disabilities in Secondary Schools in Rivers State based on Religion

S/N	Items	Orthodox	Pentecostal
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		(n = 104)		(n = 296)	
		\bar{x}	SD	\bar{x}	SD
.26	I am patient with students who read slowly or painfully	3.24	0.65	3.11	0.69
.27	I get upset with students who have trouble with spelling or written language	2.91	0.81	2.93	0.89
.28	I feel I should assist students with who cannot easily recall words by giving them more attention	3.03	0.89	3.11	0.79
.29	I give special attention to students who have difficulties in calculating figures	3.48	0.72	3.50	0.62
.30	I feel it is my duty to encourage students who always avoid activities that involve mathematics in my class	3.24	0.74	3.35	0.73
.31	I get upset with students who have difficulty in understanding simple mathematical symbols or formulae	3.46	0.62	3.46	0.69
.32	I get upset with students with illegible printing/writing	3.43	0.65	3.33	0.71
.33	I get upset with students with inconsistency in spacing words or letters	3.26	0.81	3.08	0.85
.34	I give special attention to students who always have unfinished or omitted words	3.12	0.66	3.06	0.84
.35	I feel I should assist students with cramped or unusual grip of pen	2.18	0.94	2.51	0.99
.36	I feel I should give additional attention to students who exhibit poor balance and posture in class	2.15	0.93	2.31	0.96
.37	I get upset with students who are unable to organize self and belongings	2.17	0.91	2.33	0.97
.38	I feel I should assist students with difficulties in forming words by giving them more attention	2.26	0.94	2.46	0.97
.39	I feel students with difficulty in communicating ideas can never cope with academic tasks no matter how you try	2.85	1.03	2.94	0.97
.40	I feel frustrated teaching students with who have difficulty sitting calm at a place in my class	2.25	0.93	2.26	0.95
.41	I feel I should not waste additional time on students who are easily distracted or inattentive in my class	2.35	1.03	2.41	1.02
.42	I place students who are constantly changing activities in class on front row in order to ensure their full attention	3.41	0.55	3.31	0.67
.43	I believe children with learning disabilities need to be given special attention by their teachers	3.23	0.64	3.13	0.73

.44	I can teach a learning disabled child in a general class	3.23	0.90	3.18	0.85
.45	If I have my way, I will avoid teaching learning disabled children	2.10	0.84	2.45	0.90
.46	My major business is my salary at the end of the month and not teaching children with learning disability	2.31	0.99	2.39	0.91
.47	Teaching children with learning disabilities is what I cannot do	2.33	0.89	2.34	0.91
.48	I naturally feel excited when I see children with learning disabilities that wants to learn with other students	3.01	0.82	3.11	0.77
.49	Teaching a child with dysgraphia is an enjoyable thing	2.79	1.07	3.27	0.78
.50	I try as much as possible to encourage co-teachers to attend to the needs of children with learning disabilities	2.77	0.78	3.15	0.81
Grand Mean		2.82		2.90	

Criterion Mean = 2.5, Mean: 1.0-2.49 = Disagree, 2.5-4.00= Agree.

Table 4.13 reveals the mean ratings of teachers' attitude towards students with learning disabilities in secondary schools in Rivers State based on religion. The result revealed that the teachers from Orthodox religion agreed to items 26-34, 39, 42-44, and 48-50 with mean scores greater than or equal to the criterion mean of 2.5, while on the contrary, they disagreed to items 35-38, 40, 41, & 45-47 with mean scores less than the criterion mean of 2.5. Similarly, teachers from Pentecostal religion agreed to items 26-34, 35, 39, 42-44, and 48-50 with mean scores greater than or equal to the criterion mean of 2.5, while on the contrary, they disagreed to items 36-38, 40, 41, & 45-47 with mean scores less than the criterion mean of 2.5. Consequently, the grand mean of 2.82 for teachers from Orthodox religion, and 2.90 for teachers from Pentecostal religion revealed that teachers from Pentecostal religion had a higher mean rating than their counterparts from the Orthodox religion concerning their attitude towards students with learning disabilities in secondary schools in Rivers State.

Hypotheses

1:There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of teachers' knowledge towards students with learning disabilities in secondary schools in Rivers State based on gender.

Table 3.2: Summary of Independent t-test on difference in the Mean Ratings of Teachers' Knowledge towards Students with Learning Disabilities in Secondary Schools in Rivers State based on Gender

Gender	\bar{X}	SD	n	df	t_{cal}	t_{crit}	P-value	Decision
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Male	3.23	6.00	200					
				398	1.03	1.96	0.09	Retain:H ₀₁
Female	3.20	5.26	200					

Table 3.2 indicates that $t_{cal} = 1.03$, $df = 398$, and $t_{crit} = 1.96$. Therefore, since $t_{cal} < t_{crit}$ and $P > 0.05$, then there is no significant difference in the mean ratings of teachers' knowledge towards students with learning disabilities in secondary schools in Rivers State based on gender. Hence, the null hypothesis one was retained at 0.05 level of significance.

2: There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of teachers' attitude towards students with learning disabilities in secondary schools in Rivers State based on religion.

Table 4.3: Summary of Independent t-test on the Difference in the Mean Ratings of Teachers' Attitude towards Students with Learning Disabilities in Secondary Schools in Rivers State based on Religion

Religion	\bar{X}	SD	n	Df	t_{cal}	t_{crit}	P-value	Decision
Orthodox	2.82	6.19	104					
				398	2.52	1.96	0.01	Reject:H ₀₁₁
Pentecostal	2.90	6.85	296					

Table 4.25 indicates that $t_{cal} = 2.52$, $df = 398$, and $t_{crit} = 1.96$. Therefore, since $t_{cal} > t_{crit}$ and $P < 0.05$, then there is significant difference in the mean ratings of teachers' attitude towards students with learning disabilities in secondary schools in Rivers State based on religion. Hence, the null hypothesis eleven was rejected at 0.05 level of significance.

Discussion of Findings

The result of research question one revealed the grand mean of 3.23 for male teachers and 3.20 revealed that majority of the male and female teachers showed good knowledge of students with learning disabilities in secondary schools in Rivers State, with no substantial mean difference. Furthermore, the corresponding hypothesis revealed that there is no significant difference in the mean ratings of teachers' knowledge towards students with learning disabilities in secondary schools in Rivers State based on gender.

This is in agreement with the finding of kelechi (2019) revealed that there was no significant gender difference in the knowledge of the roles of regular and special education teachers in the education of students with learning disabilities. However, a significant gender difference in the attitude of teachers

towards their roles in the education of students with learning disabilities. The result further showed that female regular and special education teachers obtained a more positive attitude towards their roles than male regular and special education teachers in the education of students with learning disabilities.

This finding supports the findings of Throndsen and Turmo (2012) that revealed no statistical distinctions based on teachers' gender in teachers' mastery goals for students and mastery approaches to instruction. The study finding is also in consonance with Wanakacha, Aloka and Nyaswa's (2018) finding showing no gender differences on motivation of teachers to perform their core functions. Thus, male and female teachers share similar level of knowledge about instructional and leadership roles for promoting quality education among students with learning disabilities.

The result of research question two revealed that teachers from Pentecostal religion had a higher mean rating than their counterparts from the Orthodox religion concerning their attitude towards students with learning disabilities in secondary schools in Rivers State. Furthermore, the corresponding hypothesis revealed that there is significant difference in the mean ratings of teachers' attitude towards students with learning disabilities in secondary schools in Rivers State based on religion. This is in agreement, However, in terms of religion teachers' the Christian teachers' community has a long history of negative attitudes towards people with disabilities. Eiesland (2009) reiterated that the church has too long provided ideological funding and charitable practices to people with disabilities which result in marginalisation. This implies that the Christian teachers' has a flawed focus on healing people with disability instead of accepting their condition. The church has to understand that people with disability are another brand of the image of God and have to be recognised in their own condition. The findings supported stated that people with disability Wolfensberger (1998) are marginalised when society views them as an object of charity or as someone who is sick and needs to be healed. He further pointed out that the Christian teachers' devalues people with disability by viewing them as the other or alien. Finally, Reinders (2008) stated that the prevailing Roman Catholic teachers' view regards the life of a person with profound disabilities as a manifestation of natural evil.

Conclusion

The study, thus conclude, that majority of the male and female teachers showed good knowledge of students with learning disability in secondary schools in Rivers State, with no substantial mean difference. Hence, it was revealed that females teachers have been found to possess better disposition towards their roles in the education of students with learning disabilities. Male teachers as much should try to research, attend conferences or programmes that will enhanced their knowledge about students living with learning disability in Rivers State and Nigeria at large. Knowledge acquired will enhance teaching and learning process of students living with learning disability . Based on religion, both Christian teachers' and the Orthodox should developed a positive attitude and stop viewing students with learning disabilities as evil or means of charity, by consistently having negative attitude it will definitely affects them academically, spiritually, socially and psychologically. It was on this note that the researcher conclude that there is no significant difference in the mean ratings of teachers' knowledge towards students with learning disabilities in secondary schools in Rivers State based on gender and there is significant difference in the mean ratings of teachers' attitude towards students with learning disabilities in secondary schools in Rivers State based on religion.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study it was recommended that:

1. Male regular and special education teachers should emulate the patience and care of female teachers in order to effectively teach students with learning disabilities in secondary schools.
2. Regular teachers and special education teachers should develop positive attitude towards students with learning disabilities in regular classrooms.
3. Teachers should endeavour to have knowledge about the education of students with learning disabilities to enable the students acquire more knowledge and become productivity to the society

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